

Di-Gozd Digital Forest Inventory-Mobile app

Introduction

The mobile application complements the web application. After registering the plot in the online application, you can make five different records. Tree count recording can be done in two ways, automatically or manually, using augmented reality technology. It is used to estimate the wood supply or to determine the amount and value of the wood mass. A recording of the felling path can be used to search for felled trees later or to control the felling.

Lessons learned

The mobile application complements the web application. After registering the plot in the online application, five different surveys can be taken. Tree counting can be done in two ways, automatically or manually, using augmented reality technology. It is used to estimate the wood supply or to determine the amount and value of the wood mass. A recording of the felling path can be used to later search for felled trees or to control felling. Mobile applications, classified as augmenting artificial intelligence system, are also contributing to digitalization and have been developed for forestry or related sectors.

Figure 1: Overview of digital platform.

For further information contact

- info@kocevski-les.si

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://di-gozd.si/>

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